

ELEPHANT

IN THE LAB

SHORT ANALYSIS

Old MacDonald had coauthors

Short title	Old MacDonald had coauthors
Long title	Bibliometrics of the 20 highest performing authors in Agricultural and Biological Sciences as well as Veterinary Science
Authors	Martin Schmidt ¹ , Benedikt Fecher ¹ , Christian Kobsda ¹
Author affiliation	¹ Knowledge Dimension, Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society, Berlin, Germany
Author bios	<p>Martin Schmidt is a doctoral researcher at the Institute of Landscape Systems Analysis within Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research and associate researcher at Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society.</p> <p>Benedikt Fecher is the programme director of the research programme Knowledge Dimension and heads the Open Science research group at the Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society.</p> <p>Christian Kobsda works as the political consultant at the Leibniz Association and is an associate researcher at the Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society.</p>
Author social links	Martin Schmidt: ORCID – ResearchGate – Twitter Benedikt Fecher: ORCID – ResearchGate Christian Kobsda: ORCID – ResearchGate – Twitter
Date published	20 July 2017
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.829998
Cite as (APA)	Schmidt, M., Fecher, B., Kobsda, C. (2017). Bibliometrics of the 20 highest performing authors in Agricultural and Biological Sciences as well as Veterinary Science. <i>Elephant in the lab</i> . DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.829998

Description

The number of authors per article in the subject area *Agricultural and Biological Sciences* is 5.2 on average with a maximum of 111 authors. The mean number of coauthors is increasing by 0.2 per year in the respective time period (Figure 1). The articles in this analysis ($n = 2710$) were cited 8.9 times on average with a maximum of 479 citations.

The number of authors per article in the subject area *Veterinary Science* is 6 on average with a maximum of 22 authors (Figure 2). The mean number of coauthors is increasing by 0.2 per year in the respective time period. The articles in this analysis ($n = 1404$) were cited 6.6 times on average and 98 as maximum.

NUMBER OF AUTHORS PER ARTICLE IN THE SUBJECT AREA AGRICULTURAL AND BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

Increase of co-authors per year = 0.2
Number of articles = 2710

Figure 1: [Boxplot](#) of the number of authors per paper in the subject area *Agricultural and Biological Sciences*. The box denotes 25–75% of the values with the median (bold line) in it. The small circles are outliers. Due to a limitation of the y-axis, some outliers are not shown. The yellow line shows a linear model of the mean number of authors per article with a confidence interval of 0.95 shown in light grey. Data source: Scopus. CC BY 4.0 Schmidt, Fecher, Kobsda.

SHORT ANALYSIS

NUMBER OF AUTHORS PER ARTICLE IN THE SUBJECT AREA VETERINARY SCIENCE

Increase of co-authors per year = 0.2
Number of articles = 1404

Figure 2: [Boxplot](#) of the number of authors per paper in the subject area *Veterinary Sciences*. The box denotes 25–75% of the values with the median (bold line) in it. The small circles are outliers. The yellow line shows a linear model of the mean number of authors per article with a confidence interval of 0.95 shown in light grey. Data source: Scopus. CC BY 4.0 Schmidt, Fecher, Kobsda.

Methodology

The results of the Advanced search in Scopus were restricted by an algorithm with

- a time period of publishing (2010 to 2016)
- the document types (articles or reviews),

- and a quantitative limitation regarding the publication output (articles by the 20 highest performing authors with the most Scopus listed articles in every subject area).

For details and code see Schmidt et al. [2017](#).

References

Schmidt, M., Fecher, B., Kobsda, C. (2017). Methodology for the analysis of authors using meta data from Scopus. [Elephant in the lab](#). [Link](#).